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Global e-Government Services

Grew on average between 2013 and 2022 by 28.05%.

Online government services, within the framework of the Global Innovation Index (GII), serve as a crucial indicator of a country's ability to leverage technology to enhance the transparency, efficiency, and accessibility of public services. These services encompass a wide range of digital applications and platforms that allow citizens to interact with the government and access various public services quickly and conveniently. Such services include the registration of official documents, tax payments, access to public information, the request for permits and licenses, as well as participation in decision-making processes through e-governance platforms. In the context of the GII, the quality and spread of online government services reflect the digital maturity and technological innovation of a nation. Effective implementation of these services can significantly contribute to improving administrative efficiency, reducing corruption, increasing civic participation, and fostering economic development. Moreover, the availability of well-developed online government services is often correlated with high levels of internet access and digital skills among the population, essential elements for sustaining an innovative ecosystem. The GII evaluates these services through various parameters, including the quality of digital infrastructure, the ease of use of online platforms, the security of digital transactions, and the inclusivity of governmental digital initiatives. An efficient and accessible system of online services indicates a government embracing technological innovation to improve citizens' quality of life and promote sustainable and inclusive development. In summary, online government services are an essential component of a country's innovation ecosystem, reflecting a nation's ability to harness digital technologies for public benefit.

Global Government Online Services in 2022. Data on government online services for 2022 provides an overview of digital maturity and the effectiveness of e-governance infrastructures in various countries. The ranking highlights a strong correlation between economic development, the adoption of advanced technologies, and the quality of digital services offered to citizens. South Korea tops the list with a perfect score of 100, followed by Estonia (99.4), Denmark and Finland (97.1), and Singapore (96.5). These countries are known for their advanced digitalization policies and adoption of innovative technologies in the public sector. South Korea, in particular, has invested massively in ICT infrastructure and implemented a wide range of online services for citizens, facilitating access to government information, healthcare, education, and other critical areas. Estonia is renowned for its e-governance model, with initiatives like e-residency and a secure and efficient online voting system. Other high-scoring countries, such as the United Kingdom (95.9), Australia (94.7), and the United States (94.7), demonstrate how advanced economies leverage digital technologies to enhance governmental efficiency and citizen interaction. These countries have implemented digital platforms that allow citizens to access public services simply and quickly, reducing bureaucracy and improving transparency. Emerging countries like Kazakhstan (92.3) and China (90.6) also achieved notable scores, showing that investment in digital technologies is not limited to wealthier nations. China, in particular, has made significant strides in digitalizing public services, using technologies such as artificial intelligence and big data to improve urban management and citizen services. European countries are well represented at the top of the ranking, with nations like the Netherlands (90.6), Sweden (90), Spain (88.8), and France (88.2) highlighting the effectiveness of their digitalization

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strategies. These countries have adopted policies promoting innovation and digital inclusion, ensuring a wide range of public services is available online. However, not all countries show the same level of advancement. Nations like Germany (73.5), which are positioned lower than other European countries, suggest there are still challenges to overcome, such as integrating digital infrastructures and widespread adoption among the population. This underscores the need for targeted policies and continued investments to improve access to and usage of digital services. Lower-ranking countries like Zambia (25.9), Guinea (21.8), and Lao PDR (19.4) indicate significant deficiencies in ICT infrastructure and access to digital services. Challenges in these countries include a lack of technological investment, low internet penetration, and limited capacity to implement online government services. The absence of Hong Kong SAR from the ranking with a score of 0 may be interpreted as a lack of available data or non-participation in the survey. The gap between countries at the top and bottom of the ranking highlights the importance of international cooperation and support to improve global digital capacities. International organizations and public-private partnerships can play a crucial role in bridging these gaps by providing resources, knowledge, and technical assistance to less developed countries. The availability of efficient and accessible online services is crucial for the modernization of public administrations and improving citizens' quality of life. A good e-governance system not only facilitates access to public services but also promotes transparency, reduces corruption, and enhances civic participation. Therefore, it is essential for governments to continue investing in digital technologies and work towards making their services more inclusive and accessible to all citizens, regardless of their geographic location or economic condition. In conclusion, the 2022 data on government online services reveals a varied landscape, with countries at the forefront of digitalization and others still facing significant challenges in improving their services. The ongoing evolution of technology offers unprecedented opportunities to enhance governmental efficiency and the quality of public services but also requires commitment, investment, and a strategic vision to ensure no one is left behind in the race toward a digital future.

Global Government Online Services between 2013 and 2022. Data on government online services between 2013 and 2022 shows a wide variety of performances and progress among different countries. This analysis provides an overview of growth dynamics and challenges faced by governments in improving the digitalization of their public services. The most significant improvement was observed in Zimbabwe, which saw an impressive increase of 312.6%, rising from a score of 12.7 in 2013 to 52.4 in 2022. This progress could be attributed to government initiatives aimed at bridging the digital divide and improving access to online public services despite the country's economic and political difficulties. Other African countries like Togo and Benin showed significant improvements, with increases of 264.9% and 161.2%, respectively. These increases reflect efforts to improve digital infrastructure and increase accessibility to online services. Nigeria and Ghana also reported notable progress, with increases of 133.3% and 110.9%, respectively. In Asia, countries like Armenia and Cambodia have made great strides. Armenia saw an improvement of 114%, rising from 32.7 to 70, while Cambodia recorded an increase of 139.7%. These advances can be attributed to government policies promoting digitalization and the adoption of emerging technologies to improve public services. In Europe, Albania and Azerbaijan reported significant improvements. Albania almost doubled its score, rising from 42.5 to 84.1, while Azerbaijan increased from 36.6 to 70.6. These advances result from government initiatives aimed at improving transparency and efficiency through digitalization. However, not all countries have shown improvements. Some, like Latvia and the United Kingdom, have reported slight declines. Latvia saw a decrease of 1.02%, dropping from 58.8 to 58.2, while the United Kingdom recorded a decline of 1.54%, falling from 97.4 to 95.9. These declines may be due to various factors, including market saturation, difficulties in implementing new technologies, or changes in political priorities. Other countries experiencing significant declines include Singapore, which recorded a drop of 3.5%, and the United States, which saw a decrease of 5.3%. These declines may indicate that, despite the high starting position, there have been challenges in maintaining or further improving access and

efficiency of online services. Some countries experienced more drastic declines. Egypt saw a decrease of 4.99%, while Qatar recorded a drop of 10.8%. These declines may be attributed to various issues, including political instability, economic problems, or lack of continued investment in digital infrastructure. Overall, the data shows that while many countries have made significant progress in digitalizing government services, others still face significant challenges in improving accessibility and efficiency of their online services. The improvements observed in countries like Zimbabwe, Togo, and Benin demonstrate that even nations with limited resources can make great strides through targeted policies and strategic investments. At the same time, the declines observed in countries like Singapore and the United States indicate that maintaining high service levels requires continuous commitment and adaptation to new technologies and citizens' needs. These data suggest that the future of digitalizing government services will depend on a combination of factors, including political will, investments in ICT infrastructure, and the ability to innovate and adapt quickly to technological changes. While some countries are at the forefront, others still have a long way to go to ensure that all citizens have access to efficient and inclusive public services.

Economic Policies to Enhance E-Government. Economic policies to enhance e-government services are crucial for modernizing public administration and improving the efficiency of services offered to citizens and businesses. Firstly, it is essential for the government to invest in advanced technological infrastructure, ensuring high-speed internet coverage nationwide, including rural and less developed areas. This investment not only overcomes the digital divide but also lays the foundation for universal access to digital services. Alongside infrastructure investments, promoting digital training among public employees and citizens is fundamental. Digital literacy programs, refresher courses, and the development of specific skills are necessary to ensure that the population can effectively use e-government services and that public personnel are prepared to manage and implement such services. Another crucial aspect is adopting policies that incentivize innovation and collaboration between the public and private sectors. Creating public-private partnerships can accelerate the development of innovative solutions and improve service efficiency. In this context, the government should also provide tax incentives and funding for businesses developing digital technologies and services for public administration. Furthermore, it is necessary to simplify regulations and streamline bureaucratic procedures to facilitate adopting new technologies and implementing e-government services. A clear and favorable regulatory framework can reduce entry barriers and encourage faster and more effective adoption of digital services. Interoperability between different public administration IT systems is another key element. Different public entities must be able to communicate and exchange data efficiently and securely, ensuring integrated information management and greater transparency. To this end, developing common standards and shared platforms that facilitate service integration and centralized access to information by citizens and businesses is necessary. An interoperable system reduces duplication and inefficiencies, improving the user experience and increasing trust in digital public services. Data protection and cybersecurity represent another fundamental pillar for the success of e-government policies. The government must adopt rigorous measures to protect citizens' personal data and ensure the security of digital infrastructures. This requires not only implementing advanced cybersecurity technologies but also defining clear policies on privacy and data protection, in compliance with national and international regulations. Citizens' trust in e-government services largely depends on the perception of security and the protection of their personal data. Another aspect to consider is promoting citizens' and businesses' participation in developing and implementing e-government services. Through participatory processes, such as public consultations and feedback platforms, it is possible to gather suggestions and ideas directly from end users, ensuring that the services developed respond to their needs. Active citizen participation not only improves service quality but also increases the sense of belonging and trust in public institutions. Economic policies must also promote the sustainability and scalability of e-government services. This means planning and implementing solutions that can be easily adapted and expanded over time, in response to technological evolutions and new societal needs. It is important to plan long-term investments and

develop sustainable business models that ensure digital services' continuity and efficiency. Another crucial element is integrating e-government services with broader economic and social development policies. Digital services can play a key role in promoting social inclusion, access to essential services, and economic development of less developed areas. In this context, e-government policies must be integrated with initiatives aimed at promoting equal access and reducing socio-economic disparities. Moreover, promoting international collaboration and the exchange of best practices with other countries is important. Sharing experiences and knowledge can accelerate progress and adoption of innovative solutions and facilitate harmonizing regulations and technical standards internationally. International cooperation can also open new market opportunities for national businesses developing e-government solutions, contributing to the country's overall economic growth. Finally, continuous evaluation and monitoring of e-government policies are essential to ensure their effectiveness and efficiency. Clear and measurable performance indicators must be developed, as well as monitoring systems that allow evaluating the impact of implemented policies and making any corrections or improvements. Transparency in results and constant communication with citizens are fundamental to maintaining high trust and adherence to digital services. In conclusion, enhancing e-government services requires an integrated and multidisciplinary approach, including technological investments, training, innovation incentives, interoperability, data security, citizen participation, sustainability, social inclusion, international collaboration, and continuous monitoring. Only through a comprehensive and coordinated strategy is it possible to achieve an effective digital transformation of public administration, improving the quality of services offered and responding to the needs of an increasingly digital and interconnected society.

Conclusions. The value of government services increased on average between 2013 and 2022 by 28.05%. Between 2013 and 2022, the value of government services increased from an average of 54 units to 69.2 units. There are countries where the value of government services has increased much

more than the average, such as Zimbabwe with a change of 312.59%, Togo with an increase of 264.96%, Benin with +161.22%, Cambodia with an increase of 139.68%, and Nigeria with an increase of 133.33%. There are also countries where the value of online government services has significantly decreased, such as Israel with -12.11%, Saudi Arabia with -13.67%, El Salvador with -14.41%, Zambia with -17.51%, and Ethiopia with -22.50%.

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